

**THE CONSTRUCTION OF LITERARY KNOWLEDGE THROUGH
BRAZILIAN LITERATURE, SPECIFICALLY THE LITERARY WORK****MARÍLIA DE DIRCEU** DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7410805***Professor Msc^a: Soraia dos Santos Rodrigues****Author Bachelor's Degree in Letters from the University of the State of Amazonas – UEA;**Specialist in Teaching Methodology of Portuguese Language and Literature; Master in**Educational Sciences from Del Sol University – UNADES in Del Este –**Anjosoraia@hotmail.com;****Prof Dr. Jacimara Oliveira da Silva Pessoa****Co-author Graduated in Pedagogy from the Federal University of Amazonas – UFAM;**Doctor and Master in Educational Sciences from the University of San Lorenzo - UNISAL,**jacypessoa@gmail.com.***Abstract**

This article presents an analytical view of the techniques developed to awaken the student of the second year of high school at the Escola Estadual Frei André da Costa of the afternoon shift in the city of Tefé for the construction of literary knowledge through literature specifically the literary work Maria de Dirceu. Above all, this study emphasized the interpretation and experience of teachers and students present in this reality, thus presenting a critical and reflective analysis of the concerns that arise due to the lack of interest of students in reading and especially in literary texts, and with the intention of emphasizing the importance of the study of literature for the high school student, leading him to have contact with a work by an author who was part of the history of our country, but who also had his ideology and therefore was prevented to live his great love.

Keywords : Studies, Literature, Students.

Assuming that Literature is the art of the word, thus, with the manifestation of literature, the craftsman of the word recreates reality from the vision that he has of the world that surrounds him, on the other hand, literary art can also be a invention, in which the author creates an imaginary, fictitious reality.

In Brazil, literature begins with the Brazilian 16th century, since a good part of it is about travel literature, according to some critics, it is more appropriate to speak of a literature

about Brazil than “Brazilian literature”.

The main literary manifestations of our Quinhentismo are: informative literature (letters, reports, navigation logs, treatises and historical reports about the new land.) and the catechetical literature of Fr. José de Anchieta, despite its pedagogical-catechetical purpose, has a literary character in itself (plays and poems.). It is also worth mentioning that this was the initial period of the germination of letters in the nascent Brazilian territory.

In fact, in the first three centuries, the social context was one of pure exploration, but this exploratory posture was of paramount importance for the creation of urban centers and in parallel with economic exploitation. There were those who manifested themselves through writing, thus giving rise to the first echoes of literature in Brazil. And all these questions are presented to high school students most of the time without a concern to awaken in the student an interest in reading. In this sense, it is evident that the non-acceptance of what is new, which is not so new, is rejected by the student and consequently leads the teacher to look for ways to work on something that, until then, in addition to not arousing interest in the student, does not part of their cultural repertoire. All that remains is for the teacher to have to comply with his students page after page of the textbook. In view of the above, it is necessary to create means to alleviate such concerns.

Although literature is not a delimited curricular component, it gains strength in the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) in which the study of literary texts is of great importance for the study of the Portuguese language, as well as in the other disciplines of art, history and geography.

In conversations with teachers, there was a concern about what to do to make reading pleasurable for the student and, in the case of high school, it is due to the study of literature and, consequently, to literary works, as they refer to texts from times the which in a first contact become unattractive to the high school student and consequently showing a certain aversion to the study of literature. It is possible to say that literature plays a fundamental role in the formation of man as a subject and citizen, because through literary texts it is possible to understand oneself and the various social dynamics of the world.

The interest, when approaching this theme, was above all to emphasize the importance of the study of literature for the student, in high school, leading him to have contact with a work of an author who was part of the history of our country, more than he also had his ideology and for that he suffered and even so he lived intensely, loved and was loved and wrote a good part of his life in lyres. Thus, the general objective of the research was: To analyze the techniques used for the study of Brazilian literature, specifically the work of Marília de Dirceu to awaken

in the student of the second year of high school at the Escola Estadual Frei André da Costa the construction of literary knowledge, in the municipality of Tefé/Amazonas/Brazil.

And for the research to become effective, the specific objectives were also used: To detail a bibliographic study about the work Marília de Dirceu in the second year of high school at the Frei André da Costa State School for the construction of literary knowledge. In the municipality of Tefé/Amazon/Brazil; Identify how techniques can be developed for bibliographic studies about the work of Marilia de Dirceu; in the second year of high school at the Frei André da Costa State School for the construction of literary knowledge, in the municipality of Tefé/Amazonas/Brazil; Point out the fact that the student considers the study of literature unnecessary in the second year of high school at the Frei André da Costa State School for the construction of literary knowledge, in the municipality of Tefé/Amazonas/Brazil.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

THE CONSTRUCTION OF KNOWLEDGE THROUGH LITERATURE

As the Greek philosopher Heraclitus said, life is movement and change. There is no aspect of life that is immune to time and change. And this thought is aligned with the literature which is linked to memory and imagination and thus passed through time serving as a theoretical basis from generation to generation.

Sartre (2004) states that Literature is, by essence, the subjectivity of a society in permanent revolution. Thus, the student's lack of interest in teaching literature and the low quality of the offer of that discipline could lead to failure in the intellectual revolution of future generations.

According to the National Common Curricular Base, in reading, the target must be the interaction between reader, listener and spectator with the diversified texts. And for there to be an improvement in reading comprehension, it is suggested that the student be provided with different experiences such as reading, listening, commenting, as well as a reflection on who wrote for whom he wrote and for what purpose, time, space, the means of circulation, in short, to lead the student to have a brief knowledge of how that text reached him. And in the course of all the accomplishment of that work, the student was given the opportunity to know the author, the work, the reason that led the author to write the work, as well as the historical context in which the author lived at the time.

Literary reading must permeate the understanding of how literature dialogues with human life, literary language and its profound stylistic construction, the fact of how it can

transcend time and space. Reading the literary text is not restricted to understanding the written language, but refers to an action of critical and responsive reception, which implies reacting to the text, giving an agreeing or disagreeing answer. Thus, the student can "react" to the literary text by writing comments, debating, parodying, recreating, creating, however, the main focus will not be on the writing model, but on the possibility of encouraging the student to establish dialogues, create their ideas, delimit your memory. (BNCC, 2017 p 507.)

In this sense, the BNCC (Base Nacional Comum Curricular da Educação) understands that, in Brazil, Secondary Education, in addition to being the final stage of Basic Education, is also a right of every citizen. However, the segment represents a bottleneck in guaranteeing the right to education, whether due to the insufficient performance of students in Elementary Education, the excess of curricular components or the distance between schools between youth culture and the world of work. Therefore, as foreseen by the BNCC, it is essential to seek the universalization of education. This is the purpose of the BNCC is to establish an egalitarian education that covers the entire national territory and takes into account the quality of education and the formation of Brazilian citizens. The Base has a normative character and establishes learning objectives defined through essential skills and abilities. Literature is contemplated in the third of the ten General Skills for Basic Education, as we can identify in the following quote: "Value and enjoy the various artistic and cultural manifestations, from local to global, and also participate in diversified practices of artistic-cultural production" . This competence is directly related to the role of the school, as it is in this institution that the student will have contact with literary texts from different times and cultures and this will make a total difference in teaching and learning.

The Base also addresses literature in an extra-school context, this is very evident due to the occurrence of the Pandemic that is now plaguing us, and among this context we have digital practices, which meet the concern of promoting quality education in line with the technological possibilities of contemporary life. This can be seen in the following quote: "After reading a literature book or watching a movie, you can post comments on specific social networks, follow directors, authors, writers, follow their work closely; we can produce playlists, blogs, minute-videos, write fanfics, produce e-zines, become a booktuber, among many other possibilities. (BNCC, Languages, Portuguese Language, Elementary School, p.68). □□

And literary studies follow the same path. The history of literature is often the focus of understanding the text; a story that does not always correspond to the text that serves as an example. (PCN High School 2000 p. 16)

Therefore, the teaching of literature must be linked to a social function, which Florestan Fernandes (1966) addresses in another article, "Social change and school education", where his thesis is: educational institutions have the responsibility of presenting social functions innovative, to then institute in man the capacity for perception and creative intelligence (Fernandes, 1966, p.86).

The reading of literary texts is not restricted only to entertainment and/or writing techniques, it goes far beyond, such an activity is linked to the student's education, consolidating their emotional and affective education, which gives meaning to how they see the world.

In this way, literature may have different functions for different readers: for some, reading a poem will serve to understand their own feelings, while for a novel the reader will be able to get to know a world different from their own, and for others, they will be able to find philosophies of a literary text in a literary text. In short, what can be said is that literature plays a fundamental role in the construction of man as a subject and citizen.

WORK —MARÍLIA DE DIRCEU

In conclusions of some authors work, Marília de Dirceu. After *Os Lusíadas*, it is one of the most widely read poetic works in Portuguese. From the 1st Portuguese edition of 1792 to the Brazilian edition, by Editora Martins, with a preface by Afonso Arinos, from 1944, there are 47 editions, of which 13 or 14 are Brazilian.

Because it is a letter, there is a pure and true feeling. The eroticism in them is not artificial, but authentic, as Carpeaux tells us (1961, p.1195).

According to Antônio Cândido, (1977, p.120). The lyrics of the work came out of the "mining experience, sharpened by the friendship with Claudio and vivified by the love of Doroteia, they are built after a long meditation around her personality and in front of the image of the beautiful Marília. They have nerve and blood, achieved by Gonzaga's mastery of the verses."

Veríssimo (1969, p.109) tells us that Gonzaga became a naturalized Brazilian, when from Marília's love, from this love, poetry emerged, which will mature when in prison, perhaps unfair, since almost nothing proves that the poet actively participated in the conjures. What is certain is that his love and prison lyrics make him a good poet of our literature and the first to sing of Brazil, with tenderness and circumstance, love.

The work *Marília de Dirceu* is the most emblematic work of Tomás Antônio Gonzaga, it is a long lyrical and narrative poem, which was published in Lisbon, from 1792. The poem is composed of 80 lyrics and 13 sonnets. The work is divided into three parts. The first part with thirty-three lyrics, which were published in 1792. The second part with thirty-eight lyrics, and

were published in 1799 and the third composed of nine lyres and 13 sonnets and were published in 1812.

THE STUDENT AND THE TEACHING OF LITERATURE

It is known that Literature is of great importance in the teaching-learning process of students, as it does not only refer to book reading, but can and should also be contemplated in other areas of knowledge, since literature is present in all civilizations, from the oldest to the current ones and represented in various means of expression, however, it can be said that literature is a cultural asset that, once put into action, contributes to aesthetic, cognitive and linguistic development.

In this sense, Martins (1986), presents us with the following information about the sensory aspects available to readers: science proves that other sense organs can be activated during reading. Reading takes place in the following fields: sensory (referring to the human senses); emotional reading (that which takes us to pleasure, responding to a personal need) and rational reading, which has the “status of the literate” (that which is capable of producing and appreciating language). He also states that these three levels of reading are interrelated, sometimes even simultaneous, as reading is a dynamic act, and the simultaneity of these three levels allows the reader to reflect and establish a dialogue with the different texts.

Unfortunately, in schools, the true value of literature is not given, the preference for grammar over literature is notorious, but anyone who thinks that literary readings do not teach how to read and write correctly and with the mediation of the teacher is mistaken, leading the student to develop a critical sense, argumentative capacity and reflections. In this sense Machado (2007) says: discover the treasure that our ancestors left us as an inheritance, consequently, we must improve it.

The author makes it clear that we need to take advantage of the knowledge of the past to understand the present that confuses us so much. Therefore, encouraging reading must be a constant concern in schools, since students acquiring the habit of reading will be included in a literate culture.

And when it comes to classic books, it goes beyond decoding. In high school, the mediator teacher should present to the students new possibilities and perspectives of the linguistic and formal aspects of the language so that as soon as he is faced with the complexities of reading and even between the lines, he can flow to the next reading with greater security.

METHODOLOGY

The research carried out was of a qualitative nature, and included the techniques used for the study of Brazilian literature, and took into account the speeches and opinions of the participating students and teachers involved in the research to understand the construction of literary knowledge, in the municipality of Tefé - Amazonas /Brazil.

According to Sampieri (2013) “the qualitative approach is selected when we seek to understand the perspective of the participants on the phenomena that surround them and deepen their experiences, points of view, opinions and meanings [...]” (p.376) The bibliographical research was of paramount importance, since the students of the second year of high school at the Frei André da Costa State School had the opportunity to build a theoretical literary foundation through Brazilian literature, as they were also able to do a critical and reflective analysis of Marília de Dirceu's work, thus, contributed to awaken interest in Brazilian literature.

The population was from the Frei André da Costa State School, students and teachers. In view of the new context imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic, the initial environment of the school research were the WhatsApp groups created in the second years of high school, classes 01, 02, 03 and 04 of the afternoon shift, in a total of one hundred and twenty (120) students and teachers of Portuguese Language and Literature. As samples, five (05) students from each class were selected, totaling twenty (20) students and four (04) teachers, in all, (24) twenty-four analyzes were carried out.

At first, through a slide class, the student was presented with concepts in various aspects of what literature is, then using the digital tool in the form of video classes, the Arcadismo literary period was presented with its contexts, characteristics, authors and works in Next, research was proposed about the complete biography of the author Tomás Antônio Gonzaga and another research about the Inconfidência Mineira movement, where Tomás Antônio Gonzaga was part.

Then the field research with exploratory methods, where semi-structured questionnaires were applied, with semi-structured interviews, it is worth mentioning that the works were all carried out in a virtual environment in the period of April and May 2021.

Data collection began with observation in second-year high school classes, taking into account how students develop the ability to read and interpret literary knowledge, as well as identifying needs in building the profile of the student reader. Due to the situation caused by the Corona-virus pandemic, this observation took place through the application of a

questionnaire via WhatsApp. According to (King and Horrocks, 2009) “the qualitative interview is more intimate, flexible and open”. (Sampieri p.425)

The second phase of the research took place with the participation of the students in the bibliographic studies and then with the application of the techniques which were developed together with the students. The study began with a presentation of the history of Brazilian literature, the Arcadismo literary movement and the life and work of the author Tomás Antônio Gonzaga and the historical context of the Inconfidência Mineira movement in which Tomás Antônio Gonzaga had an important participation.

Each group developed a technique, where the first group 01 carried out the Reading Techniques; the second class 02 Comics; the third group 03, with the Poetry Recital and the group 04 with the Dramatization. It is worth mentioning that the techniques reported here were developed about the work “Marília de Dirceu, at the Frei André da Costa State School in the municipality of Tefé - Amazonas / Brazil.

Through the development of techniques, the researcher participated as an applicator and mediator of the proposed works, and she was able to record the entire development of the facts so that they could be analyzed, interpreted and presented in the final considerations together with the results of the interviews with the teachers and students. selected. This action is in line with what is recorded in the book *Metodos de Pesquisa* by Sampieri (2013), where he states that “The researcher should never forget who he is and why he is in the context. (p. 418)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

When developing the research, the difficulties of the second year students of the Frei André da Costa school were identified, in developing an interest in literature and in dealing with literary texts, even more so, not identifying the real social, historical and economy that can be found in books, causing these students to distance themselves from any stimulus that sought to change this “literary blindness”.

And the teachers' concern regarding this problem was quite visible. And the previously reported problems had a new aggravating factor, with the event of the Covid19 Pandemic, the said students had left the elementary level and entered the high school level. It is known that the first year of the pandemic was very impactful, both for students and teachers. Schools had to close, and until teachers adapted to the new methodologies, it took a considerable amount of time. And also the psychological conditions of students and teachers. All these mentioned events contributed to a gap in the students' knowledge of teaching and learning, since the

technical and grammatical norms of the Portuguese language were valued and prioritized, with the result that some contents were ignored.

And for the beginning of the works, the first specific objective was used: To detail a bibliographical study about the work Marília de Dirceu in the second year of high school at the Frei André da Costa State School. This objective was of great value, since this work opened a range for a historiographical study, the author, Tomás Antônio Gonzaga, was part of a group called Inconfidentes. From this group develops a very important historical event for our country, the “Inconfidência Mineira”. The study also had knowledge about the period of Arcadianism, which happened in the eighteenth century, as this time is known as the century of lights, that is, a moment in which a scientific vision of the world is developed. In the course of the work, it was observed that it was through this study that the students became aware of several events about the early history of our country, which made it clear to the researcher that it was the only way they understood why, to celebrate the 21st of April, like the day of Tiradentes, and this is considered a martyr of the Inconfidência Mineira, with this there was an awakening of the historical and cultural appreciation of Brazil, however, this factor still needs to be even more completed and improved, which will occur over the course of teaching and learning process, as this project served as a starting point for new projects alluding to the theme.

The second specific objective that identified how techniques can be developed for bibliographic studies about the work Marília de Dirceu, in the second year of high school at the Frei André da Costa State School, with this, it was found that the use of various techniques has an effect positive, when it is intended to arouse in the student an interest in the study of literary texts, since the teacher leaves the complacency and seeks to innovate, it is expected that there will be a significant return on the part of the students, who wait for this change, because the generation that we find in the classroom today are active students who are always looking for news, with technological reasoning, which makes their attention somewhat volatile. The choices of techniques were made through bibliographical readings, where four techniques were chosen to be worked on in the second year classes. As there were four classes, a technique was applied to each one. All the techniques achieved the objectives proposed in the research, however, for the researcher, the class that stood out in terms of performance and interest was the 2nd year 02 class, in which the applied technique was comics, where it was observed that there was a commitment of all the students, who were able to transform the work, which in its nature has a formal language, into drawings that conveyed sensitivity through verbal and non-verbal language, which became more accessible. In this aspect, it was understood that there was

not only a reading, but an interpretive reading whose central objective is to give meaning and life to what is being read.

The third and last objective, which led the researcher to point out the fact that the student considers the study of literature unnecessary in the second year of high school at the Frei André da Costa State School for the construction of literary knowledge. As already emphasized in the research, by teachers and students the reason why there is not a greater active search for literature in the school environment is the fact that the library does not have a collection aimed at the reading preferences of the students, however the library of the Frei André da Costa state school has a wide range of paradidactic books, but with a technical language, that is, which for some becomes inaccessible. In this sense, it is concluded that when the techniques were applied by the researcher, there was a significant improvement in terms of interest in searching for a book available in the library. This statement was verified through informal conversations with some teachers who observed the change in the students.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In view of the above, the hypothesis is confirmed that despite the fact that students arrive at high school with little interest in reading, and specifically in literary texts, work of a social nature can be done through literature, which may involve this student in the midst of History of his social context and thus awaken to obtain knowledge that previously did not interest him. From the studies of the historical context in which the work “Marília de Dirceu” was inserted, the students were able to know in an autonomous and pleasant way the historical information that the world was going through. The word autonomous was due to the fact that some research was proposed to the students, among them from the Inconfidência Mineira movement, and it was pleasant because a knowledge competition was carried out about the contents contained in the research. The event was very fruitful, the students held a healthy competition, but the one who scored the most won, but what really won was the knowledge acquired by all.

The hypothesis is confirmed that the role of the teacher as a mediator of self-knowledge in the realization of the techniques to be developed, of any nature of transferring information is of paramount importance and how the application of the techniques could not be different both in online classes and in hybrid classes, because at this moment the teacher directs the student to autonomy so that learning develops. Generating the construction of literate reader students. And the last hypothesis is also confirmed, in terms of believing that the teacher seeks

to innovate through varied methodologies, whether using the types of reading, dramatization, drawing, recital, parodies, in short, using the student as the protagonist of his know-how, both student and teacher. teacher will reap good fruits. And it was in the applications of the four techniques that the researcher innovated her methodologies, applying the same work “Marília de Dirceu”, using varied techniques, that is, one in each group. And in response, objectives were achieved and hypotheses were satisfactorily confirmed. It is important to point out that every commitment and effort that the educator uses in his classes and especially in the study of literary texts will contribute significantly to the student's education.

The negative point raised by the researcher was the fact that, as a result of the Covid 19 pandemic, some students stopped returning to school, for a number of reasons ranging from financial, where those responsible lost their jobs in the city and had to return to school. life in the countryside, and others had to help support themselves at home, found work on the day shift and were reassigned to the night shift, and even the psychology of many was affected and they did not feel safe returning to the classroom. And today the school's great challenge is the active search for these students, which was mentioned earlier. What is regretted is that these students lost a good opportunity to receive the knowledge developed during all stages of the project.

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